

Exploring Search for Self and Self Actualization in The Guide and Siddhartha

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Abstract

This thesis analyzed the struggle for search of self and for self-actualization in The Guide by R.K Narayan and Siddhartha b Herman Hesse under the vision of existential philosophy. The chief argument of the paper is how far the protagonists have been successful in their struggle for actualizing their selves. The thesis found out that existential elements exist in the journey for self-actualization and self-search of both the protagonists of the novel. It also examined that freedom of choice, and spirituality. However, differences in their struggle were also found to some extent. This is qualitative research in nature where the texts of both novels were analyzed. The thesis will contribute to the field of research psychology and literature. These elements if embodied in a person, s/he can become painstaking, self-reliant and self-motivated.

Introduction

In the past, existentialism was a warm part of the intellectual property. William Barratt's books such as 'Man's Search for meaning' were sold and read by countless people. This theory became famous in the years of World War II in the twentieth century. Existentialism is a form of enquiry that discovers the nature of existence by emphasizing experience of the human subject not merely the thinking subject, but the acting, feeling, living human individual. Existentialists believe that man is born without purpose into a world that makes no sense but each person has the ability to create his or her own sense of meaning and peace. The focus on freedom of individual in existentialism is related to the limits of responsibility one accepts, as an outcome of the individual's freedom. Individualism is the belief in independent thought or action. The focus on individual freedom in existentialism is related to the limits of responsibility one accepts, as a result of one's freedom. The key thing is that existential freedom cannot be repudiated or withdrawn, only disavowed. It is disavowed when we refuse to acknowledge that we have a choice and insist that our actions are determined by our circumstances. For examining how one searches for self and achieves self-actualization, Narayan's *The Guide* and Hesse's *Siddhartha* are selected for the study. The *Guide* shares similarities with Herman Hess's *Siddhartha*. *Siddhartha*, which goes through an illusionary maze, embraces spiritual heights. The existential struggle turns into a mystical journey later on. There are many similar dimensions in both texts. *Siddhartha* is an Indian tale as Herman Hess himself mentioned this thing in the subtitle of the novel. On the other hand, *The Guide* is a story of an Indian boy who goes through different phases of life. Bhatia examined, "These different stages pass from his father's assistance to full-time independent railway stallholder, from the stallholder to a seasoned guide, from *The Guide* to a lover and manger, from the manger to model prisoner, from the model prisoner to a saint finally" (122).

Like Raju, *Siddhartha* also stays dissimilar period of life and experiences when he joins Samanas, after that his meeting was with Buddha, then he becomes a lover of Kamala and later he experiences a merchant and becomes richer in his experiences and eventually attains mystic heights through long existential struggle as Raju.

Narayan, commonly known as R. K. Narayan, was an Indian writer known for his work set in the fictional South Indian town of Malgudi. The fictional town of Malgudi was first introduced in *Friends*. His 'The Financial Expert' was hailed as one of the most original works of 1951. *The Guide* is Narayan's classic fiction highlighting the social context and everyday life of his characters. He has been compared to William Faulkner who also created a similar fictional town. As a novelist, R.K Narayan, his novel *The Guide* is his most famous novel which represents the concepts of dharma and karma. This was the first novel in English literature which won the national award of Sahitya in New Delhi. The concepts of dharma and karma are deeply rooted in Hindu moral law (Atkinson 21). *The Guide* also has the patterns of dharma and karma. Innate capabilities and

deficiency are defining junctures of one's personality yet choices have a vital contribution towards the making of one's being. "The theist in Hindu philosophy believes that Dharma or law is pre-establishing by the lord but it does not predestine man's fate, for each individual has free will. No external fate or force his fate. Man determines the architect of his fortune" (Makodia 64). Hermann Hesse was also a prose writer. He received the Nobel Prize in literature 1946. During 1911 and 1912, he showed his interest in Eastern culture and religion. For this purpose, he visited India and that trip brought about his best-known novel, *Siddhartha* (1922). No doubt search for truth is the major theme in Hesse's work. In 1946, Hesse gained Nobel Prize for literature, and in 1962, Hesse died.

Statement of the Problem

Man always conceives himself an existing being and tries to generate the meaning for his existence. Existence gives him freedom to give an access to the different aspects according to his will. This thesis thus investigates how the protagonists of the selected novels approach to their goal. It also explores the issue of self-realization of the protagonists, and their struggle for self-search. The study focuses on the way Raju in *The Guide* and Siddhartha in *Siddhartha* how they pursue ends how they sustain their individualism and existence in the world.

Methodology

This study is qualitative in nature. The textual analysis of two continental novels is carried under the theory of existentialism by analyzing the lives of the protagonists of selected novels. The paper focuses on the self-search, freedom of choice, self-realization, anxiety, and spirituality, and meaningless of the protagonists of the selected novels.. This search for self changes into realization when a person is immersed deeply into the experiences of the world. The study uses Soren Kierkegaard's perspective of existentialism that is related to human freedom. He states that existence is the most valuable for human being and it is always in the process of becoming something. It states that individual freedom, Self-actualization finds the truth of life and understands 'who I am' and 'who has created me'. He believes that man has to make his existence.

Review of Literature

Different critics and scholars have perceived the novel, *Siddhartha* from different perspectives. Imran and Iftikhar declared that the name of the novel *Siddhartha* itself carries the theme of a search for self-realization.

Siddhartha

The word *Siddhartha* is made up of two words in the Sanskrit language, 'Siddha' which means achieved and 'artha' means what was searched for; that is, he who has found the meaning of existence". In this novel, *Siddhartha* understood his own existence through his own experiences and in term of freedom of choices. They explored that the protagonist *Siddhartha* achieved the mission of self-realization. He found his self after a great travelling (78). Prays explored a similarity in a comparative study of Indian epic Bhagavad Gita and *Siddhartha*. *Siddhartha* is an Indian tale which deals with physical journey to a spiritual journey and Bhagavad Gita is an Indian epic and in both purified soul is achieved through a physical journey. She compares *Siddhartha* with Gita and states that the same situation is in Gita chapter 3. "The essence and goal of pilgrimage are considered to be the purification of the soul in the Gita which is achieved by *Siddhartha* as examined in the paper, "He attains wisdom through a physical journey to simultaneous spiritual journey" (3). Colin Butler provides some critical objections to *Siddhartha*. *Siddhartha* has a puzzle mind and wastes his time with shamans and so many for the purpose of achieving the truth of life. Tekel, in his book, analyzed four novels of Hermann Hesse in the light of religious vision. In his abstract, he expresses that Hesse believes that religion is the name of the aesthetic realm, services of life and inner journey. He states that the theme of religion is repeated in his many novels. In his novel, *Demian*, inner world and self-identity is the basic thing for which one has to struggle for finding his self or reason of life (30). According to her analysis, Hesse believed in individualism. And he constructs a journey where the individual discovers his self alone. For this purpose, social norms are violated in his work (31).

The Guide

Researchers have examined the novel *The Guide* from different angles. Some researchers have discussed the novel from a religious perspective, while others describe it as the existential novel, subcontinent novel, realistic and or romantic.

Rani, in her paper, *The Existentialism in R. K Narayan's The Guide*" declares that in *The Guide* the major characters have an existential vision. She presents the play as an existential play. She realizes that Narayan's

characters have free will and they make their lives according to their choices. Sharma explored that R.K. Narayan's writings show the Hindu religion and myth. In the Hindu religion, god is considered in the form of "OM" (13). Hindu culture is divided into four castes which are the Brahmin, the Kshatriya, the Vishay, and the Shudra. Roy investigated R.K. Narayan's *The Guide* and he states that his romantic view of life is mingled with social reality in a very dynamic way (34). Kumar opined that Raju, the protagonist of *The Guide*, appears in the sense of poly guide. In the novel, Raju played his role as a guide of railway people after that he showed his guidance for tourist and in this way he helped Roise and became her guide. After the prison, he went to a village where he helped the villagers and became their guide. Chinnam explained that *The Guide* is a story which has two storytellers, and the novel is divided into two parts. The first part is in Malgudi and the second part is in Mangle. Swati and Vasatave declared that resistance is the major theme in postcolonial literature. In *The Guide*, there is a conflict between tradition and modernity. Christy criticized *The Guide* which reveals the Indian culture and tradition. According to him, *The Guide* is the reflection of Indian culture, tradition, custom and religion. In *The Guide*, Narayan tells the lifestyle of Indian people. Christy analyzed the characters and atmosphere of *The Guide* and concludes that it is a mirror of India. It tells the poverty and ignorance of India people and the villagers of India live a backward life and no doubt they have a soft and kind heart. The caste system is the major issue in Indian culture and R.K. Narayan depicts the story where Roisie is unaccepted able for Raju's mother because of her low caste. *The Guide* is a story of India as he says, "The traits of Indians manners and customs are reflected in this novel". (71). Khan examined *The Guide* which carries the sub-continental as well as universal elements. She examines these elements and states the universal ingredient as love, jealousy, sex and money. Bhatia examined that the hero of the novel Raju realizes his identity and he changes from a railway guide to a spiritual leader of a big crowd. Sarkar analyzed *The Guide* through the lens of Gandhi's economic theory. Shoo explained in the novels of R. K. Narayan" express his consideration about the place of Malgudi and he compares Malgudi with sir Walter Scott 'board countries' and it compares with 'Lake District' of William Wordsworth, 'The Wessex' of Thomas Hardy, or 'five Towns' of Arnold Bennet. In this imaginary place, Narayan characters are living a compound pattern of lives. Malgudi plays the role of hero in Narayan novels and stories (98). Important characters are lives in Malgudi such as Raju in *The Guide* Swami in *The Bachelor of Arts* and Krishnan in *English Teacher*.

Data Analysis and Discussion

This part of the paper explores the existential struggle for existence of being in *Siddhartha* by Herman Hesse and *The Guide* by R. K. Narayan. The analysis is categorized under two sub headings including search for self and self-actualization. In both parts, the protagonists' struggle of search for self and self-actualization are comparatively analyzed by using the texts of both novels as data source.

Search for Self

Human beings are always in the process of becoming and human existence. Jean emphasizes that no one in the world guide in our life. We must make our decision and we are alone to produce a moral decision in our life and judge our moral choices (20). Siddhartha has the same feelings as stated: "Nobody showed the way, nobody knew it, neither his father nor the teachers and wise men, or the holy song" (9) meaning that he believed in his own choices. This also happened to Siddhartha, and he shows his doubt about gods "And what about the gods, Was it really Prajapati who had created the world? Was it not Atman, he alone who had created it? Were not the gods form created like me and you, moral, transient? (9). In the beginning of this novel, it is described the Siddhartha's inquiry about his self. "But where was this self this innermost? It was not flesh and bone, it was not thought or consciousness. That was what the wise men thought. Where, then, was it? To press towards the Self, towards atman _ was there another way that was worth seeking?"(9). Consequently, he decided to leave his home for the purpose of searching the self. According to Sartre, individual existing is a process of becoming (348). It also happened to Siddhartha when he said to Govinda as: "I suffer thirst, Govinda and on this long Samanas path my thirst has not grown less" (19). Siddhartha feels disturbed at this house because of his father's anger. But later he leaves it his decision. Then his father realized that he will no longer remain with him at home as he has already left him (14). Then Siddhartha gains experiences from Samanas from Buddha and from Kamala. When he leaves Buddha, he thinks many questions and asks himself what he wants to teach? And what he wants from teachers. Then he replied to himself that he wants his self as stated, "And he thought: it was the self the character and nature of which, I wished to learn, therefore, I wanted to rid myself of the self to conquer it" (36). This thought shows that he was penetrating his self by saying that one must find the source within one's own self, one must possess it. Everything else was seeking a doctrine. These were Siddhartha's thought; this was his thirst, his sorrow" (10-11) and he must gain experiences himself" and must try (44). Therefore, he leaves Buddha and totally changes his thought. He thinks that the struggle of search self through any teacher is not fruitful for him and he will learn from himself saying "I will learn from myself the secret of Siddhartha" (36). Here, the "secret of Siddhartha means one can say the inner of Siddhartha or his self. After the experience, Govinda asks Siddhartha what he is now (82). He replied that he does not know (82) He knows as little as he

and he also tells Govinda what he will be tomorrow he does not know" (82). This statement corresponds to his confusion about his existence. He doesn't know, and how his existence will be as Sartre says that it is correct that the most important thing for human beings is his existence (33) and man's existence is not final until he is always in the procedure of becoming. For him, human beings are always moved from possibility into reality. Due to his freedom, it is possible. It is also said that human existence is due to the decision of his life. In this novel, Siddhartha is in the process of becoming with the help of his own decision like Raju who is the hero of R. K. Narayan's novel *The Guide*.

In *The Guide*, Raju finds his self. But unlike Siddhartha, he has not one goal in his life but through his experience, he knows the real meaning of life like Siddhartha. He has been representing a person who only gains experiences and through this, he recognizes his self. Raju leads a meaningless life. He does not know the fact of life. There is something in his personality which forces him to become him a poly guide. Like Siddhartha, something is missing in Raju life and that is achieved at the end through experiences and freedom. He became a railway Guide "I was beginning to have a sense of ownership of the railway" and gain experience from them. (16). Sartre is considered as the existentialist who believes in subjectivity and for him, life is meaningless individual makes its value with the help of experiences. Like Siddhartha, Raju seems to follow Sartre's views. In this manner, Raju gains experiences in his life telling Velan that he has learned much from scrap (49) meaning that he is in the process of becoming and his existence is not final. Raju says "I am seeing a lot of places and getting paid for it" (58) through many places, through experiences which make him a perfect being and give a meaningful life.

Accordingly, it was Raju's search which makes him poly-guide, and which forces him for a journey like Siddhartha. When he becomes Roisie's guide, he experiences the love of woman but his experience is not satisfied and he has to go to jail. Although he is struggling for his existence, yet he crosses many steps of his journey but he does not know what can he do and where can he do? When robber asks him he replied "I don't know must go somewhere. (16) This statement represents Raju search is not end.

The struggle of Raju and Siddhartha has some similarities. Both have spent their lives pass through different stages of the world. Behalf on self-existence Siddhartha and Raju continued their whole journey till they attain spirituality. Through the experience of different stages, both search their meaning and attain the purpose of their existence.

So, self for search is a basic theme in *The Guide* R.K. Narayan and in *Siddhartha* by Hermann Hesse. *Siddhartha* passes different stages of life to find his self and at the end when he gains spirituality his search is ended. His different experiences help him find the inner. And at the end, he said to Govinda kiss his head and gain calm, peace. In *The Guide*, Raju experience a different phase of life and through experience understand the real meaning of his life, when he takes twelve days fast he comes to know this experience give him pleasure. After reading the searching life of Siddhartha and Raju the reader can state that there is a similarity of both lives with the existential philosopher. As existentialists believed that it is an individual struggle which brings his existence.

Sartre states that human beings are actively involved in every activity that happen in every kind of situation (130) as mentioned above Siddhartha and Raju are involved in every activity for the purpose of his search existence Kierkegaard gives three phase of human existence. Hence, in aesthetic phase, human beings get pleasure through their sexual instinct and also are controlled by it. Raju and Siddhartha make a sexual instinct with Roise and kamala. For Sartre, in aesthetic phase, the individuals mostly depend on public and have no personal future (134) as mentioned above Raju and Siddhartha goes different stage and mostly depend on public and gained experiences. Above quoted texts express Raju and Siddhartha stages which are depend on public, both are aesthetic, when they search their selves and try to recognize themselves.

Self-Actualization

Self-actualization is a moment when an individual finds the truth of life and understands its purpose. Sartre believes that self is recognized when a person attends the world easy and know its meaning when anxiety. (23)

Siddhartha, although in the start, his friends have the same feeling of suffering and anxiety, however, at the end, Siddhartha "comes still nearer quite close and kisses her on the forehead" (125). When Kamala meets Siddhartha on the bank of the river, she asked Siddhartha and whispered if she attained it? She asked if he had found peace. He smiled and placed his hand on hers (99). Here, his smile is the answer of Kamala, and after seeing the smile, Kamala replied that she had felt and seen it. This statement shows that Kamala has examined him find his self as stated that it was over; he had awakened: he had indeed awakened and had only been born today" (37). Siddhartha's success is in process towards finding the self. He thinks that he was born then because he began to wake and know about his nature and the book of his own nature (ibid 37). His thoughts refer to the process of organizing his self as, through an expression of his inner fatigue, he feels some sort of satisfaction. Then, Vasudeva says to him that he waited for this hour, his friend. Now it had arrived and 'now it completed" (116). It is in such a manner that Govinda knows as he has perfected one smile" (126). Here, Siddhartha recognizes his self and understands the meaning of life everything was done to him and he attains a great peace.

His peaceful smiling face is observed by Govinda telling that Siddhartha was silent and looked at him with his calm, peaceful smile (125).

In *The Guide*, Raju attained his self when he saves humanistic values. His existence became meaningful, when many people became to depend and attained his self when he states that ‘by avoiding food I should help the trees bloom and the grass grow, why not do it thoroughly? As it was the first time he was learning the hill of full application, outside money and love and it was no more than a supplication to the heavens to send down rain and save humanity Raju finds the meaning of his life when he ‘doesn’t speak to anyone, but if he looks at you, you are changed’ (30) shows that Raju meaningless life gains meaning. His existence once to create and he creates his own world.

Man can become whatever he wants to become through his choices (Sartre 20). Siddhartha continues his journey, and nobody is there to stop him. It was Siddhartha himself who makes this suggestion of journey and says that ‘Tomorrow morning my friend, Siddhartha is going to join Samanas (12). He uses his choice freely when no longer remains with his father at home.’ (14), and was about to intend to stand and wait the whole night (13). Then, Siddhartha joins Buddha that was his own decision and it was his freedom which energy him to leave him “...since this man’s teaching has not done so” (33). His reply to his followers according to their own choice shows his free will when he states, ‘I must judge for myself’(33) and then his discourse that ‘everything needs only my agreement, my assent, my loving understanding, then all is well with me and nothing can harm me.’(121).

In *The Guide*, there is freedom for every character. The hero of the novel, Raju acts according his free choice. He became a railway guide according to his own will’ when he utters that he’d also like to be served to you” (87). “Then he became Roisie's guide and spent his time with her. It was his own choice to live in Velan village after out from the prison and due to his freedom, Raju becomes a poly guider. As Rani States, “Raju’s basic need is to ‘exist’ and to exist he has to act and so in the novel, he acts as a guide, as a lover, as a manager and finally as a Swami.”(2) All his action shows his free will and choice. He acts according to his will. In *The Guide*, Raju all action shows his free will. Although his mother did not agree, Roisie was staying with him show his own will. “I intervened to say, Mother, she is not going anywhere; my mother appealed to me... she can’t go anywhere, mother as she has got to stay here” (172). Similarly, he leaves seducing Roisie when he was asked to “have some senses, Raju. She is another man’s wife. She must go back to him” (172) but, even then, Raju lived with her on his own choice. So he does not care about his mother advice. His conversation with Roisie ‘you are not leaving. I am going to be here and you are going to be there (171) and then his talk with a teacher that ‘he means that if he wants a place he can have it (46) shows his consideration on freedom” and then he addresses Roisie “I want you all to think independently, of your own accord and not allow yourselves to be led about by the nose as if you were cattle” (52). It shows that Narayan wants to present Raju as an existential figure who believes in liberty. When Raju becomes Narayan’s mouthpiece saying “until you try, how can you know what you can or cannot do” (52). Raju is forced to pour out his existential point of view to make his existence visible, and then he advises Velan and his friend that they should work freely, and in this way, they can understand the abilities which they have.

In *Siddhartha*, Siddhartha represents as a person who believes in freedom and who uses free will, and due to his freedom, he makes his self and attains self-actualization. Like Siddhartha, Raju acts according to his own will throughout his life, as a free person. He has also advised the villagers to act according to their own will and free will. For Raju and Siddhartha, the most important thing is their existence, their actuality, and freedom. No doubt, Raju and Siddhartha’s actions reach them to achieve to what they are and how they can act freely.

Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

The study showed how freedom and free will lead to know one’s existence. The has been centred on Raju who is shown as a free person in *The Guide*, and through his free will, he realizes the purpose of his existence as the situation is same in *Siddhartha*. Like Raju, Siddhartha is also free from any power and due to his freedom he first joins Samanas but leaves them; then he leaves Buddha’s teaching; he also leaves Kamala and makes a decision to spend his life with Vesud. Here, he finds the purpose of his life. Hesse demonstrates his anxiety at the start of the novel when Siddhartha wants to leave his home for his search of self. A similar situation is in *The Guide*. Raju’s change ‘from a railway guide to tourist guide to villager guide’ shows his anxiety. Moreover, both heroes strived for their identity and achieved by knowing the truth of their lives. Similarly, they find their inner reality at the end of the novel. The study also examined how man feels when is free. Unlike Raju, *Siddhartha* believes that only the individual makes his world. No one can do anything for him, not any teacher not even god. A free man can face all type of situations with boldness because he is not bounded by any type of rules and regulation of any society. Such people never face any difficulty because the weapon of freedom helps them to select their ways of life and make their own world. Freedom of choices, free will, free action and free decision are required to get a lofty, ludicrous situation of the human race. In this fast and depressive life, freedom of choice can make one’s self-reliant and independence which are the most

important factors for one's existence. A free person is free from the oppression and all the social and traditional norms. Consequently, this thing makes him not only psychologically reliant but also economically strong. So freedom of choice is necessary in this modern and scientific age in order to ensure progress in this age. Stylistic analysis of the novels can also be done to explore the effects of the text on the readers. The researcher will identify the language habits of the novelists.

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